

STUDY OF COMMERCIAL PREPREGS BY TORSIONAL BRAID ANALYSIS (TBA)

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Abstract

TBA (Torsional Braid Analysis) provides every one who has an interest in composite processing with a great number of informations of all kinds. Various aspects of this usefulness for fiber/resin prepreg characterization are presented including control of products, prediction and optimization of cure cycles, estimation of resin fluidity, assistance for the development of new resins, control of prepreg ageing.

Introduction

The fabrication of more complex parts of increasing dimensions in composite materials involves the use of a great deal of fibers and resins as prepregs. As these prepregs are often little known and badly controlled products, it is quite important to improve the situation, taking account of the constraints on the production conditions :

- cost of initial products (fibers and resins),
- cost of workmanship in the handling and stacking of prepregs sheets and tapes,
- necessity of shortening the occupation times of production appliances, by reducing first the number of preliminary mouldings, then the duration of the full-size parts production.

Obviously, it is desirable to turn the moulding step into a continuously controlled process. Several methods are investigated currently, based on the informations provided by the reacting resin : dielectrometric analysis, ion graphing..... In spite of some obvious disadvantages - for the methods make necessary some preliminary calibration for each class of products - they will certainly develop in the coming years. Up to that time, more conventional methods may contribute to the knowledge of the resins and to understand more about them in realistic conditions.

One of these methods is TBA (Torsional Braid Analysis ; in French, ATMI, i.e. Analyse par Torsion de mèche imprégnée) which has the advantage of analysing the thermo-mechanical evolution of the prepreg sample throughout the different states of the resin. So the method is considered to be well fitted to the study of such a process as moulding.

Development of TBA originates in Gillham's work (1, 2). The method, which was

adapted from the torsion pendulum, just arose from the wish to better understand the transformations of macromolecular substances when they are heated. For a few years, it has been used to watch the hardening of epoxy type resins, see Gillham (3, 4) and Haskins (5).

We used it in a somewhat different way : strictly, in TBA, a braid of nylon or glass is impregnated by a liquid resin, whose cure is to be analysed ; in the present work, the material to be examined is the as-received commercial prepreg itself, whatever reinforcement, fiber or fabric, it has. The prepregs are purchased or gained in a more or less advanced condensation state (B-stage), in contrast with most of the studies on the curing of epoxy resins, where carefully purified products in stoichiometric proportions are dealt with. But the main purpose in this work is to collect informations for helping the moulder in his planning control work, not for the chemist to conclude on the reactional mechanisms of well-defined species.

1. Method and equipment

The prepreg samples are cut from the as-received sheets (dimensions : 60 x 10 mm, nominal thickness). According to the TBA test sample configuration, the reinforcement (as a fabric or aligned fibers) acts as the supporting element of the resin system to be studied. In most systems, the resin turns into a liquid when heated, and there is no sufficient torsional rigidity of the sample to allow the oscillations to be recorded. This can be readily overcome in providing the sample with a thin plate of a stiffener, which is only a monopoly of pyrolyzed unidirectional carbon-resin prepreg. As the resin melts, the stiffener is wetted by the resin, and prepreg sample and stiffener remain bonded together ; the coefficients of expansion of both elements are also perfectly fitted to each other. The test sample is photographed with its carbon-carbon stiffener and heads on Figure 1. The heads, made of fine woven metal mesh, maintain enough anchoring and tightening, even when the resin is wholly liquid.

Fig. 1 — Prepreg test sample.

- a) ready to use sample with heads and stiffener,
- b) unidirectional tested sample.

The tests have been performed with a ZWICK torsion pendulum (type Torsiomatic 5203). The test sample is mounted in an oven with an inertial disk hanging at its lower end. The upper end is rigidly attached to a device periodically submitted to torsion pulses. Either a clock or a digital thermometer trigger the oscillations, providing measurement intervals of 2, 5, 10 minutes or 2, 5, 10 °C.

The free damped oscillations are sensed by phototransistors and time values extracted from them, and printed out on punched tape. A computer program, with output on tracing-table, gives the evolution of rigidity R (in fact the square of the frequency) and damping factor Λ as a function of time and/or temperature.

The oven is designed to carry out isothermal or heating up runs. When changing the mode, cures exactly reproducing the real cure cycles in autoclave or press, including hold steps at constant temperature, are performed. The resulting curves for each of the three modes are illustrated in Figure 2 (a, b, c) for a standard epoxy containing one resin and one hardener. Subsequent reheating of the material, cured in given conditions and cooled down, gives the glass-transition temperature, Figure 2 (d).

Fig. 2 - Working modes of TBA.

a) isothermal run, b) heat-up with constant heating rate, c) programmed run with hold steps, d) determination of the glass transition temperature on the cured material.

R : rigidity - T : temperature - Λ : damping factor - t : time.

2. Product control at reception

In the present state of development of composite technology, formulators and impregnators are continuously in quest of better and safer products. So, there is a constant evolution of resin systems and the customer is not always informed of the consequences when a component is discarded and replaced by another. Beyond the usual methods of control (IR, DSC ...), a batch may be confirmed in TBA to be the same as the previous one, not only by its composition, but also by its thermomechanical behaviour.

In Figure 3 are shown the TBA isotherms at 160 °C of two carbon/epoxy prepregs. In both materials, the resin was given as the BSL 914 resin by CIBA (U.K.). The prepregs were obtained from different sources and analyzed in early 1975 and in late 1976 respectively. The aspect of the curve (a) in Figure 3 for the earlier material is usual in TBA (see ref. 3) with two transitions associated with gelation and glassy transition respectively. The curve (b) of the "new" material is more complex : there are several less distinct damping peaks associated with a slack two-parts rigidity curve. Moreover, these two parts have an inverted concavity, as compared to the strong increase in rigidity in the earlier material. Finally, the curing reaction is apparently not completed after several hours at 160 °C. The "new" 914 system appeared to cure slower than the earlier one.

Fig. 3 - Isotherms at 160 °C for the BSL 914 resin.
a) GRAFIL HMS/914 batch 1871/75 (analysis early 1975)
b) GRAFIL HTS/914 batch 75/2215 (analysis end of 1976)

Differences in damping and rigidity cannot be quantitatively assessed in a rigorous way because the sample is cut at random from an heterogeneous prepreg sheet whose distribution of fibers and resin varies from place to place. There is also a chemical shrinkage which

causes the samples to deform throughout the test crosswise according to the fiber direction in unidirectional samples (see Fig. 1b).

However as can be seen on Figure 3, curve a, the earlier 914 resin has little rigidity during the first minutes at 160 °C, and the increase is sudden and sharp. When the two materials are compared, looking at the time when baseline and first slope intersect in the rigidity curve, the values of Table I are obtained for various isotherms.

Table I. Change of rigidity of various prepregs

Temperature (°C)	Time for intersection (minutes)	
	old 914	new 914
140	100	50
150	65	24
160	40	19,30
170	26	9,30
180	19	8,30
190	14	6,30

The "new" 914 resin starts to harden earlier, but hardening is slower after a moderately fluid stage. These statements are in good agreement with the informations collected when the two materials were moulded. They strengthen the impression that the 914 resin formulation was somewhat modified during the period 75-76.

3. Cure planning

Getting back to the Gillham's technique, TBA may guide the moulder into the choice of the proper cure cycle. The necessary knowledge to exert this choice for a given prepreg is provided by the following operations :

- a series of isothermal tests in a practical domain of temperatures, T_i (no reaction $< T_i$ < decomposition) ;
- a computation of the activation energy of the different processes (gelation, glass transition) ;
- from the activation energies, computation of the time required for complete cure using several model cycles with or without isothermal hold times ;
- a series of tests according to the afore mentioned cure cycles to confirm the validity of the previous model.

This plan was applied to the study of various commercial prepregs. Illustration is given here for the carbon/epoxy prepreg CODE 69 (Fothergill and Harvey, U.K.) for its behaviour is typical of several presently available products (e.g. T300/5208, HTS/DX 210 ...).

In Table II are given the times, taken from the isothermal runs, corresponding to gelation and glass transition. Comprehension of the data depends on the convention which is adopted for counting the time. In Table II, the first three values t_1 , t_2 , t_3 were obtained according to Gillham's convention (Fig. 4). To get the fourth value t_4 , it is necessary to know the rigidity at room temperature before and after the isothermal experiment and the glass transition temperature of the cured sample. The latter value is consistent with the preceding ones. It will be noticed that, at 110 °C, the times for the two transitions are the same : it is the temperature noted as T_{gg} by Gillham.

Table II. Isothermal test of Code 69 (batch 1638 C125/69/48)

Temperature (°C)	Time to gelation (minutes)				Time to vitrification (minutes)			
	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4
100	> 400	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
110	150	270	—	—	150	280	—	—
120	100	180	160	165	130	240	320	—
130	60	100	110	95	92	180	230	—
140	35	45	60	50	67	130	140	—
150	26	30	40	42	38	85	95	92
160	12	15	25	23	22	57	65	58
170	7	8,30	15	11	15	32	36	40
180	5,30	5,30	—	9	10	23	—	—

Fig. 4 - Counting times from isothermal runs (from Gillham's).

From the data of Table II, Arrhenius plots were drawn for $\text{Log}_n t$ vs. $1/T(^{\circ}\text{K})$, and the apparent overall activation energy of either transition graphically determined. In Figure 5 are put together the Arrhenius plots for the gelation of different prepreps; with the CODE 69 material, three of the other systems that had been studied have been included, especially the two BSL 914 batches of the preceding section. Data corresponding to the time t_1 have been selected for the figure, but the calculated activation energy does not change, whichever t is taken.

From the isothermal runs and values of activation energy, two methods are available to predict the time-temperature, whatever the cure cycle (6).

— Reducing the cycle to a succession of heat-up steps at a constant heating rate and of isothermal steps. The extent of cure during the hold times directly results from the preceding data from isotherms. The extent of cure when the temperature increases is given

Fig. 5 - Arrhenius plots for gelation time t_1 .
 (Note the difference between the two batches of 914 resin).

by a linear combination of short isothermal holds balanced by the heating rate. A similar method was successfully applied by Carpenter (7) who studied the curing process by viscosity measurements and DSC.

- Another method based on the principles of chemical kinetics and using only the activation energy as determined before : putting the energy and one value of isothermal gelation time at any temperature T , the extent of the reaction can be deduced when the temperature increases from T_1 to T_2 and/or during a hold-time at T_2 .

Finally, the data have been compared to the results of typical cure cycles. In Table III, the calculated and experimental gelation times are listed for cycles including a hold-time at the final temperature, the first computation method being used. The product is the carbon/914 resin of the earlier batch (see section 1). Generally, the calculated times are slightly longer than the real ones ; this is related to the fact that, in the computation, transformations below the temperature noted as T_{gg} are not taken into account, which is incorrect. Moreover, the linear combination of short isothermal extents of cure is wrong according to the real shape of the curves giving reaction rate vs. temperature ; here is another cause of inaccuracy.

Table III. Comparison of experimental and calculated gelation times. Fibredux 914 (batch 1871/75)

Heating rate (°C/minute)	Hold temperature (°C)	Gelation time t_1 (minutes)	
		Experimental	Calculated
1	190	155	160
2	190	89	88,30
	180	88	90,30
3	190	63	64
	180	67	67,30
	170	72	74
	160	83	87
	150	102	105,30

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Heating rate (°C/minute)	Hold temperature (°C)	Gelation time t_1 (minutes)	
		Experimental	Calculated
3,5	190	55	57
	180	57	61
	170	66	68
	160	80	81
	150	96	97
4,5	190	44	48

4. Period for pressure application

When thick parts have to be moulded, rheological and thermal parameters must be taken into consideration to optimize cure cycles ; with an increasing number of plies, the resin must keep fluid longer, until the reinforcement has been thoroughly wetted and the porosity suppressed. As a consequence of both the heat produced by the appliance and the exothermicity of the reactions, there is a temperature rise that must be maintained within acceptable limits.

TBA gives no indications on the thermal aspect. On the other hand, it can tell how long the resin keeps its fluidity, how the viscosity changes with time/temperature and when the full pressure is to be applied, if not from the start.

In Figure 6 is given a TBA record for a carbon/914 prepreg sample heated at a rate of 120°C/hour : the rigidity decreases up to 160°C, which is the onset temperature. This temperature does not depend on the quantity of stiffener added to the prepreg piece in order to get enough torsion response in spite of the resin fluidity : this was confirmed by a manually operated experiment with a sample without stiffener.

Fig. 6 – Rigidity vs. temperature for carbon/914 prepreg.

Moreover, we noted a strong relation between the resin viscosity, when known, and the rigidity of the prepreg determined by TBA. Such a relation exists for the 914 resin whose viscosity vs. temperature variation is given in the manufacturer's data book. It is illustrated in Figure 7 for the temperature range 80 to 160°C, the temperature where rigidity inversion due to gelation is observed.

Fig. 7 — Relationship between resin viscosity and oscillation period for carbon/914 prepreg.
 a) 1°C/minute stiffener 3 mm wide,
 b) 2°C/minute stiffener 3,8 mm wide,
 c) 2°C/minute stiffener 6 mm wide.

It may be noted that neither the mass of stiffener nor the rate of heating up do influence this relation which has the form

$$\text{Log}_n \eta = A - Bt$$

in which t is the oscillation period of the sample.

It may be concluded that, with TBA, there is a permanent access to the viscosity of the resin. The informations are valuable in particular when viscosity data on the resin are available. When the TBA rigidity curve is examined for a given cure cycle, the time to apply full pressure can be precisely determined with regards to the viscosity of the resin at that moment. For a process in which the pressure is initially applied, the conditions of heating may be selected to preserve a suitable fluidity of the resin, necessary for wetting up and homogeneization of the stacking of plies.

There is also a relation between viscosity and damping factor, but it is rather irregular because this property is more sensitive to the conditions of testing. Some bumps may interfere and affect the expected linearity. Further aspects are discussed in section 6.

5. Help to the development of new products

The PSP resin, conceived and investigated in ONERA (and manufactured by Société Nationale des Poudres et Explosifs (SNPE), Paris, France) is a thermosetting thermostable resin which gives composites of outstanding mechanical properties. An excellent fire resistance and a good moisture resistance make this resin attractive for a number of applications. Numerous mouldings succeeded before TBA was applied. The designated cure cycle is as follows : 3 hours/200°C + 2 hours/250°C for a prepreg formerly dried at 150°C.

TBA diagram of GRAFIL HTS/PSP prepreg is illustrated in Figure 8 for the 200°C isotherm. Note that, after the first three hours, the curing process is not completed. Usually, full pressure is applied after 60-90 minutes in heated press ; it is the value t_1 of intersection between the base line and the slope of the rigidity curve. (Prepregs being introduced into the press set at temperature, the time to 200°C of the stacking of plies is very short and the comparison with the isothermal run quite valid).

Fig. 8 - Isothermal curing of GRAFIL HTS/PSP prepreg (batch LDG 183)
a) 200°C isotherm - b) 250°C isotherm of a 3 hrs/200°C pretreated prepreg.

To achieve complete cure, 2 hours at 250°C suits perfectly well, as can be seen from the 250°C isotherm of the preceding 3 hrs/200°C cured prepreg (Fig. 8b). The step at 250°C is then necessary to maintain the cure time within reasonable limits.

As a new resin, transfer of PSP from the laboratory to the production plant is the occasion of new problems ; to solve them, TBA can be helpful.

On Figure 9 are presented the Arrhenius plots for the time t_1 of two different batches of PSP resin manufactured, one in a pilot-plant in 1975 («1975 PSP»), the other in a larger plant in 1977 («1977 PSP»). Initially thought as minor modifications, changes in the synthesis and the formulation have been seen to lead to very different cure behaviours : the 1975 PSP, reacting slowly below 230°C, recovered a «normal» kinetics from this temperature. Rather unexpected was, on the other hand, the behaviour of the 1977 resin under cure conditions : no gelation was observed after the first three hours at 200°C ; the stacking of plies still had a rubbery consistence.

Although the network of the cured PSP does not issue from the interaction between an oligomer and a hardener, as for epoxies, the differences in the two batches of PSP may be explained by the same concepts Gillham introduced to give an account for the epoxy behaviour under curing conditions, namely :

- competition between gelation and vitrification in the range 200-230°C for the 1975 PSP ; so the time t_1 which is plotted vs. temperature in Figure 9, curve a, characterizes different events according to the temperature ;

- gelation yielding a rubbery network in the same range for the 1977 PSP ; here t_1 characterizes a single process.

Fig. 9 - Arrhenius plots for two carbon/PSP prepregs.

The differences stated in the shape of damping peaks for the two materials support this point very well : massive peak resolving into two separate peaks at temperatures exceeding 230°C for the 1975 resin ; well defined peak for the 1977 resin, followed by the appearance at higher temperatures of new peaks, possibly associated with vitrification. Further investigation on the behaviour of the PSP resin - including new batches - is now in progress.

The purpose of the preceding discussion is to show how TBA can give support not only to the moulding specialist, but also to the understanding of the steps leading to the formation of the macromolecular network.

6. Evolution of prepregs on storage

Some prepreg systems suffer a rapid evolution when stored for a long time, even when they are kept in a cool place. Other systems, with improved life, replace them gradually, but a systematic control is frequently required. TBA allows an easy control in good conditions (see also section 2).

One conclusion is sometimes that the material is still "good for service" using the manufacturer's cure cycle, though surpassing the anticipated shelf life. Occasionally, TBA control results into modifying the hitherto inapplicable standard cure cycle in consideration

of the material evolution : the product may be "saved" by means of a slight modification of the cycle and produce a sound composite. These possibilities provide a means to save money in a technology where initial products are still expensive.

In the preceding section the example was given of prepregs based on the PSP resin whose stability has been maintained during $2^{1/2}$ years at 4°C : the isotherm 200°C of the aged prepreg shows the same characteristics as the original's. But here, the processing temperature is high and a good stability at low temperatures is to be expected.

For a "low temperature" resin system, a glass/polyester based on isophthalate has been studied (388 T 12, Stevens-Génin, France). The product was delivered with a 6 months shelf life at $0. + 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. TBA diagrams according to the manufacturer's cure cycle are represented on Figure 10, both for the as-received prepreg and for a $2^{1/2}$ years, $- 18^{\circ}\text{C}$ stored product. Observed differences are collected in Table IV.

Fig. 10 - TBA diagrams based on real cure cycles for the 388 T 12 glass/polyester system. Plain lines : as received prepreg - Dotted lines : $2^{1/2}$ years long, $- 18^{\circ}\text{C}$ stored prepreg.

Table IV. Differences observed during storage of a glass-polyester prepreg (388 T 12)

	As-received	$2^{1/2}$ years long storage at $- 18^{\circ}\text{C}$
Gelation time (t_1)	After 5 minutes on the 120°C hold	At 115°C during the heat up
Minimal fluidity	$50 - 110^{\circ}\text{C}$	$100 - 110^{\circ}\text{C}$
Minimal damping	After 10 minutes on the 120°C hold	No minimum

Indeed, both materials resulted into perfectly sound composite plates for the same cure cycle according to the vendor's instructions (pressure was applied on start). Observed deviations in TBA are therefore inconclusive as far as processing is concerned for this very material. Work is still in progress on this prepreg.

There was another stability study on Modmor 2 carbon fibers impregnated with the formerly available ERLA 4617 (CARBOFORM, Fothergill & Harvey, U.K.) ; from sheets stored at room temperature were periodically cut samples for TBA tests. Results are given in Figure 11 for the evolution of the damping factor. The simplified cure cycle was : from room temperature to 160°C at a rate of 2°C/minute, plus a 160°C hold time. Diagrams for the samples 0,10 and 47-day storage are presented, the sample 0 being for the moment where the sheets were removed from the congelator.

Fig. 11 - TBA diagrams of unaged and room temperature aged Modmor 2/ERLA 4617 prepregs.

- a) 0 days R.T. aging (previous storage at cold not included),
- b) 10 days, c) 47 days.

ERLA 4617 is concerned with the general behaviour of cycloaliphatic epoxies just as studied by Gillham (4). According to him, the damping peak or shoulder on the 160°C hold may be associated with gelation. But this transition is largely dominated by phenomena which take place at about 50-100°C and whose identity is questionable : they give rise to a doublet more and more intense, moving progressively towards higher temperatures ; they are possibly glassy transitions of advanced portions of the room temperature unstable mixture.

It is noticeable that these low temperature transitions are missing in the behaviors examined by Gillham, who worked on pure, unpreheated and unaged products. On the other hand, they are present in the paper published by Hudson (9) on dielectrometric analysis of curing process in related resin systems such as CODE 69 and CODE 87. The author does not take these low temperature effects into consideration but points out any-

way that the shape of the dissipation curve (very similar in most cases to the thermomechanical damping curve) alters with prepreg age. In our opinion, these abnormal transitions are likely related to the tackiness of prepreps as well, another important aspect in composites technology.

ERLA 4617 disappearing, there was no strong incitation to know the impact on the moulding process of the above irregularities and to find an explanation for them ; so the study was given up. But a program is actually under way in cooperation with the Aérospatial Company (SNIAS) whose purpose is to set the maximum of correlations between the prepreg characteristics obtained by several methods (GPC, TBA, IR, DSC) and their capacity to be moulded after long storage at -18°C and at room temperature. Beside the aforementioned glass/polyester system, the program is including such products as T300/5208 and 914 resin reinforced with carbon, glass and Kevlar.

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